

PEDAGOGICAL CONTENT AND CONDITIONS OF STUDENTS' DEVELOPMENT OF ANALOGICAL CONCLUSION SKILLS IN RELATION TO HISTORICAL REALITY

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Abstract: In this article, theoretical-methodological foundations of students' development of analogical conclusion skills in relation to historical reality, methodology of students' development of analogical conclusion skills in relation to historical reality are studied. Also, pedagogical content and conditions of students' development of analogical conclusion skills in relation to historical reality are analyzed.

Key words: historical reality, analogical conclusion, skill, pedagogical process, professional-pedagogical activity, integrative, corporate, national, historical, technological, competence, innovative model, technological system.

INTRODUCTION. Historical awareness, historical memory and historical thinking can be formed based on the development of students' skills of making analogical conclusions about historical reality. On the other hand, the historical outlook enables students to have a wide range of historical thinking. The development of students' ability to draw analogical conclusions in relation to historical reality is based on a number of factors, and some scientists have interpreted these factors as tools. Philosophical and political studies focus on the material and spiritual factors of developing the skills of understanding history, and the study of socio-psychological factors takes a leading place in scientific research in the pedagogical and psychological direction.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODS. Scientific research works on formation of knowledge and skills about historical reality, development of historical consciousness and memory, improvement of historical thinking J.Anderson, D.Blazar, S.A.Henry, K.Halbert, Helen Timperley, Aaron Wilson, Heather Barrar, L.N.Aleksashina , V.V.Barabanov, P.A.Baranov, L.S.Bakhmutova, O.Y.Strelova, M.V.Korotkova, M.T.Studenikin, N.N.Lazukova, Y.M.Persanova, E.Yusupov, J.Tulenov, A.Begmatov, N.Zhorayev, A.Choriyev, O.Gaibullayev . Nishonova, U. Mahkamov, E. Turdikulov, R. Safarova, B. Adizov, A. Choriyev, Sh. Mardonov, D. Roziyeva, N. Egamberdiyeva, Sh. Shodmonova, Sh. Sharipov, O. Jamoldinova in their scientific research found his reflection.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION. Fiction in the historical genre, which is a component of spiritual culture, reflects the nation's past, longing, joys and sorrows, and way of thinking. In the works of this genre, the priority of the ideas of love and mutual kindness gain a positive significance in the life of the nation, while the dominance of inhuman ideas, superficial coverage of the past, leads the nation to ignorance and loss of its identity.

According to A.S. Ochildiyev, fiction written in the historical genre becomes a role model by illuminating the history, the life path of ancestors, their bravery, and becomes the original educator, an important factor that awakens the historical memory of the nation. "Past Days", "Scorpion from the Altar" by A. Qadiri, "Navoi" by Oibek, "Mukanna" by H. Olimjon, "Treasure of Ulugbek" by O. Yakubov, "Starry Nights" by P. Kadirov, "Humayun and Akbar" historical

works of art and films and plays based on them played and continue to play an important role in the growth of the historical memory of our nation. Their value is determined not by the fact that they are connected to a specific historical person or period, but also by the fact that they help to create a holistic image of the people's culture, customs and traditions, typical of a certain period of life and thinking. At the same time, it can be said that by reading such literature, the reader is influenced and enjoys the described event, and a positive imitation of the main characters of the work occurs. In addition, respect for one's ancestor, his activities and behavior, and the feeling of following an example will arise.

Based on the analysis of research carried out so far, we found that it is necessary to classify the factors of students' development of analogical conclusion skills in relation to historical reality into the following four groups: socio-political, national-spiritual, psychological and pedagogical.

The works of the first president I. Karimov fully reflect the following methodological foundations for the development of historical thinking: the idea of national identity awareness; priority of national identity; the idea of nation and patriotism; "There is no future without historical memory" principle; The idea "Self-awareness begins with knowledge of history"; "From a strong state to a strong civil society" idea; "Do not destroy the old one before building a new one" philosophy; The idea of "ending the addiction of thought, the slavery of thought"; The idea of "restoring national statehood and its modernization"; The idea of "restoration and development of national historical value and spirituality" and others.

There is no doubt that the works of our president Sh. Mirziyoyev serve as the most important program for developing students' skills of making analogical conclusions about historical reality. President Sh. Mirziyoyev's "Critical analysis, strict order, discipline and personal responsibility should be the daily rules of every leader's activities", "Rule of law and ensuring human interests - the guarantee of the country's development and people's well-being", "Free and we will build a prosperous, democratic state of Uzbekistan together", "We will build our great future together with our brave and noble people", "We will resolutely continue our path of national development and raise it to a new level", "The consent of our people has been given to our activities is the highest value", "The work of a people whose intention is great will be great, their life will be bright and the future will be prosperous", development of historical thinking in works such as "The Strategy of New Uzbekistan", based on this basis, he decided on a new way of thinking acquisition issues are covered in depth.

The development of the students' ability to draw analogical conclusions in relation to historical reality requires taking into account the influence of many psychological factors. Including self-awareness, i.e. the inclination and desire to self-evaluate; comparing himself with other people; freely, openly and meaningfully express their thoughts; Emotional characteristics such as the ability to listen to the opinions of others and the ability to compromise, and the development of the personal motivational sphere are important in this process. The process of developing the skills of drawing analogical conclusions in relation to historical reality is also related to the development of the intellectual activity of young people. Intellectual skills include the development of memory; development of perception; the development of imagination; reflects the development of attention.

Intellect is a personality trait, the ability to clearly and deeply reflect objects and events of objective existence in our mind with their specific connections and laws. It appears in all

mental processes, first of all, in thinking and creative imagination. It is more often observed when solving a bright new problem independently.

The development of the skills of drawing analogical conclusions in relation to historical reality is related to emotionality. It is necessary to eliminate negative emotions in students and replace them with positive ones. For example, it is necessary to arouse love for people. At the same time, it is necessary to develop a sense of self-confidence in young people in various situations. If loving others is the attitude towards others, then self-confidence is the attitude towards oneself. That is, the formation of the sense of "I" in the narrow sense in young people. In addition to love and trust, the ability to give up one emotion and call for another, and to learn to control fear, also refers to the emotional causes of important psychological factors.

V. I. Morasanova in her article "Individual self-control and human character" pays special attention to the problem of character typology. In his opinion, the problem of setting character typology and features is more natural and is solved methodically and rigorously in the theories of the personality factor. Here, character traits and types are considered as factors of different order, described as qualitatively different levels of personality structure. In the study of character typology, the author takes a subjective approach to the study of the psyche, looking at it from the point of view of the developmental characteristics of conscious self-control. Here, self-control is studied as a psychological mechanism of subjective activity. The results of his research show that individual self-management not only provides an opportunity to control the appearance of character, but also confirms that self-management is connected with the formation of character and the development of personal direction.

It is necessary to recognize the leadership of pedagogical factors in the development of students' skills of making analogical conclusions in relation to historical reality. These factors are also characterized by the fact that they express the socio-political, national-spiritual and psychological factors described above. The development of the students' ability to make analogical conclusions about historical reality is undoubtedly the basis of national education. From this point of view, the opinions of the scientist M. Kuronov, who was the first to study the scientific-pedagogical foundations of the organization of national education in Uzbekistan, are noteworthy. The concept of "national education" has a multifaceted scope: goal-oriented educational activity based on national values; a unique form of universal education specific to each nation; means of preservation, restoration and development of the nation and its culture (UNESCO principle); A component of the objectives, tasks and principles of the National Personnel Training Program of the Republic of Uzbekistan; a private, spiritual source of the process of comprehensive development of children of different nationalities; the main principle of educating students in moral, hard work, patriotism, beauty, economy, ecology and other directions; a humanistic way and means of fostering the culture of inter-ethnic dialogue and, as a result, achieving universal harmony in Uzbekistan; Pedagogical condition of harmony of social education and school education; the pedagogical way of leading humanity to universal harmony; a strategic object and means of ensuring national security on the social and moral front; This is evidenced by the purposeful formation of national (auto and hetero) stereotypes in students and the process of spiritual enrichment.

CONCLUSION. The first stage of national education is characterized by the weakness of national knowledge, a more vague understanding of one's national belonging, and a lack of clear understanding of commonalities with people belonging to one's nationality. It is an important requirement of today to direct family education to a clear goal, to make parents

sufficiently aware of national values and the pedagogical and psychological foundations of family education. Also, at the first stage of national education, language is of primary importance. It is known that language is one of the main components of national self-awareness. Because the language is understood as the mother tongue, and representatives of this nation speak to each other in this language. Through the national language, mutual understanding among the members of one's nationality, national cultural information, information, and cultural heritage are preserved from generation to generation.

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